

INTEGRATED TEACHING OF CHEMISTRY IN SPECIALIZED SCHOOLS WITH ENGLISH

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Annotation: The article covers the prospects of teaching chemistry and English language subjects in integration. When it entered the database from chemistry, the problem of the need to know English in acquaintance with the scientific work carried out by scientists of the world was covered. In the process of integrated lessons, the most effective forms of work on chemistry and English language bonding were considered.

Keywords: English, chemistry, integrated lessons, performance forms for each class, bachelor, master, doctorate.

Today, without the science of chemistry, which determines the scientific and technical potential of the country, it is impossible to develop social progress without the development of specific natural sciences. Obtaining new knowledge in chemistry, like any other exact science, is not possible without exchanging information, including among specialists who speak different languages. Qualified chemistry teachers should be aware of all the innovations that have arisen in the field of science abroad, as well as receive useful information. To do this, knowledge of English is required. Society needs academically literate teachers who can master and use information not only in their native language but also in a foreign language.

In the process of reading, the English language includes the study of the general cultural worldview of a person, acquaintance with the Customs and customs of other countries, mastering new methods and methods of communication, that is, frequent performance of the general development and

educational function. To a greater extent than in other educational subjects. This allows us to consider a foreign language not only as an acceptable means of integration of Science with the subjects of the humanities, but also with the subjects of the Natural Science cycle.

Thus, without knowledge of the English language, the integration of chemistry education into science is not possible. Unfortunately, the problem of integration of chemistry and English language in school is not given much attention, perhaps because of this lack of interest of teachers of Natural Sciences language adequately prepare and therefore use of science relations with the area in which they are not studied. "There is little serious research on this topic in Uzbek methodology of teaching chemistry. If many works are devoted to the integration of foreign languages with the humanities, then the question of its integration with the sciences of the cycle of Science and technology has not been sufficiently developed in domestic science and practice. There are separate studies on the integration of foreign language and chemistry.

Science the basis of integration is "language", "chemical language" and "English". English is a multifunctional natural alarm system, it is used as a means of communication, as a means of knowledge and professional activity. Chemical language is a system of concepts and rules used to express chemical information. It is a complex artificial language, rich in terms, etymology goes to different languages of the world. The organization of work on the development of knowledge in the field of chemistry in the conditions of integration with a foreign language includes several features:

- attracting students to active communication in a foreign language in various communicative situations due to the content of the topic;
- continuous monitoring of students ' achievements in order to diagnose and take into account the formation of Science and information and communicative competence;

- use different visual supports.

The most effective forms of work for the connection between chemistry and a foreign language can be science and popular texts, articles from magazines and lessons using teaching-methodical manuals and selected courses. In the secondary school, the science of "chemistry" begins to be studied from the 7th grade. By this time, students have a good knowledge of English, which allows wide the possibilities of its application. However, the stock of knowledge in chemistry is still minimal, so it is worthwhile to first study the biographies of famous scientists, as well as interesting chemical phenomena, small volumes of texts related to discoveries in physics and chemistry.

As the knowledge in the field of chemistry increases, the interdependence of Sciences will consist in the formation of the skills and competences necessary for working with special literature in English, relevant to the relevant branches of Science and technology; the ability to integrate into students the skills of reading and translating a simple special text that understands special terminology, abbreviations, etc., In secondary school, the level of knowledge increases, which makes it possible to work with texts of a scientific nature, but to work with such texts "special preparation is required, since the vocabulary of scientific texts exceeds the norms established in the program. Therefore, relations in this case begin with the assimilation of a special dictionary, abbreviation, character, etc. and work on the text (reading, translating, speaking, working with grammatical material). When working with a foreign language text, whose subject is associated with scientific achievements, you need to use a method of step-by-step collection of lexical material, which allows you to formulate practical language skills. Working with text is the best way to make a reserve of foreign words in chemistry. One of the first integrated lessons is "period law and period system D.I. Mendeleev". This topic was considered at the beginning of the study of chemistry in the 7th grade and is well suited for mastering new knowledge through an

integrated system of lessons. As an example, from the textbook M.M. Kutepova "English for chemists". You need to find and write words related to the science of chemistry.

When studying chemistry in the 8th grade, you can use a foreign-language conversational style. The teacher is able to prepare questions, in response to them, the students show their knowledge (from chemistry) on the subject of the lesson, as well as learn to express their thoughts in a foreign language. Also, students should learn to write questions on paragraph materials in English. As an example, the following questions are asked on the topic "Sulphur and its compounds" / sulfur and its compounds (8th grade).

1. What allotropic modifications of sulfur are known to you?

Oltingugurtning qanday allotropik modifikatsiyalari haqida bilasiz?

2. What are the physical properties of sulfur? *Oltingugurtning fizik*

xususiyatlari qanday?

3. In what compounds sulfur occurs in nature? *Oltingugurt qanday*

birikmalarda tabiiy ravishda uchraydi?

4. What chemical properties of sulfur make this application possible?

Oltingugurtning amalda ishlatilishi qanday kimyoviy xossalarga asoslangan?

5. What practical application has free sulfur in everyday life?

Oltingugurtdan kundalik hayotda qanday foydalanish mumkin?

The most difficult type of work is listening. This type of work allows you to develop the ability to perceive information by ear. In the process of listening to the chemical text, it is certain difficulties in the process of understanding it, because the text contains chemical terms. To simplify the task, the teacher can write unfamiliar words in advance, after listening, a discussion is held and a new chemical material is written, which is necessary for the study of the subject.

An important element in the study of Chemical Science is the development of knowledge obtained by solving chemical equations and issues. Solving problems and performing exercises can also be done with the help of a foreign language. For example, the card function can have the following contents: Complete and balance the following reactions:

2. How many grams of copper oxide (II), formed by the decomposition of 39.2 g of copper hydroxide (II)?

3. Write a balanced equation for the reaction and specify its type: nitric acid + calcium hydroxide = calcium nitrate + water.

The use of this type of work, for example, to prepare lectures and essays in secondary school or first-year students, allows students to express their opinion on the topic of interest to them, which in the future may be associated with their professional activities. The English language allows them to expand the vocabulary on this topic and acquire new knowledge from foreign sources. The following topics can be suggested:

1. *Polimerlar nima?* What are polymers?
2. *Qaysi oynaga organik deyiladi?* What kind of glass is called organic?
3. *Nega penoplast(ko'pik) shunchalik yengil?* Why is foam so light?
4. *Avtomobil shinalari nimadan yasalgan?* What are car tires made of?
5. *Saqich asosi nimadan iborat?* What is the basis of chewing gum?
6. *Qog'oz nimadan olinadi?* What is paper made from?

7. *Kraxmal va paxta momig'ining umumiyligi nimada?* What is common between the starch and cotton wool?

In conclusion, such forms of work will increase the students' interest in the science of chemistry and help to better assimilate the material. The use of the English language in chemistry in integrated lessons allows "free access to the global network, expanding the geography and space of the issues under study. It allows monitoring and comparison of a wide range of situations using primary sources of Information". Integrated lessons allow the teacher to teach the child from the first steps of learning the holistic picture of the world. Secondary school students have the opportunity to show themselves as a specialist in Chemistry, who knows a foreign language through integrated lessons.

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